

Awareness and Participation of Undergraduate Students in Information Literacy Programmes for the Use of Digital Information Resources in Selected Universities in Kano State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper examined the awareness and participation of undergraduate students in information literacy programmes for the use of digital information resources across three selected universities in Kano State, Nigeria. The study sought to determine undergraduate students' level of awareness of information literacy programmes and to examine the extent of their participation in these programmes for the effective use of digital information resources. A quantitative research method was employed using a cross-sectional survey design. A proportionate random sample of 388 final-year undergraduates from Bayero University Kano, Northwest University Kano, and Skyline University Kano was selected. Data were collected using a validated and reliable structured questionnaire and analysed using descriptive statistics, including frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations. The findings revealed that students demonstrated moderate awareness of information literacy programmes, particularly traditional formats, but showed limited awareness of specialised digital literacy areas such as citation management tools, research data management, and open educational resources training. Participation levels were similarly modest, with high engagement in introductory information literacy activities but low involvement in advanced, research-oriented programmes. The study concluded that, while information literacy programmes exist, they remain insufficient in depth and scope to fully support advanced digital resource use. It therefore recommended embedding information literacy (IL) programmes into the curriculum, strengthening awareness strategies, and expanding specialised, hands-on IL training to enhance students' digital competencies and academic preparedness.

Keywords: Information Literacy, Awareness, Participation, Use, Digital Information Resources, Undergraduate Students.

Introduction

The rapid expansion of digital technologies has reshaped how individuals access, evaluate, and apply information, making information literacy (IL) an essential academic skill. First introduced by Paul Zurkowski in 1974, IL now encompasses the competencies required to recognise information needs, locate credible sources, evaluate content, and use information ethically (Sahabi et al., 2019; Manthiramoothi et al., 2019). The American Library Association (2000) and CILIP (2018) similarly define IL as the ability to effectively identify, assess, and utilise information. The growing digitalisation has heightened the importance of IL in academic environments, where students rely heavily on digital information resources (DIRs) for learning and research (Ali, 2020).

According to Edegbo and Emumejaye (2025), DIRs include e-books, e-journals, databases, institutional repositories, multimedia, mobile apps, AI tools, and open educational resources. These resources enhance access to current scholarly materials, support remote learning, and promote global collaboration (UNESCO, 2019). Consequently, UNESCO and other global bodies advocate integrating IL programmes into national educational systems. Universities worldwide have responded by implementing orientations, workshops, and structured IL instruction, yielding positive outcomes (Mohtar & Mohamad, 2023).

Despite these efforts, studies have shown persistent disparities in IL awareness, participation, and use of digital resources. Research from the United States and Britain has indicated high awareness but inconsistent user competence (Tenopir et al., 2015). Findings from Asia and Africa revealed mixed levels of awareness and programme participation (Manthiramoorathi et al., 2019; Anaraki & Babalhavaeji, 2018). In Nigeria, some studies, such as Oyedipe et al. (2018), have reported high IL awareness, while others noted low skills and poor utilisation of DIRs (Akpojotor, 2016). Key obstacles included insufficient IL training (Nirmani, 2025), inadequate ICT infrastructure (Adejo, 2020), poor internet connectivity (Mosha & Bea, 2014), limited faculty support, and outdated digital collections (Mungwabi, 2019). These challenges continue to hinder students' effective use of digital resources.

In Northwest Nigeria, particularly in Kano State, research on IL programmes and DIR utilisation remains limited. Although universities in the region offer IL initiatives, empirical evidence on students' awareness, participation, and programme effectiveness is scarce. The study investigates the awareness and participation of undergraduate students in information literacy programmes for the use of digital information resources at three selected universities in Kano State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The rapid growth of digital technologies has made digital information resources central to higher education, providing students with convenient access to vast online journals, e-books, databases, and learning platforms (Akindele et al., 2021). Despite this abundance, many undergraduates still struggle to navigate, evaluate, and use digital resources effectively due to inadequate information literacy (IL) skills (Shamin & Priyanka, 2016). In response, academic libraries have introduced various IL programmes, including orientations, workshops, training sessions, and one-on-one support, to strengthen students' competencies. However, studies across Africa continue to report low IL levels among undergraduates (Adzakpa, 2022; Rasaki, cited in Baffour et al., 2017; Tachie-Donkor & Ezema, 2023). This is the case for undergraduates at Bayero University Kano, Northwest University Kano, and Skyline University Kano. While previous research highlights gaps in undergraduates' ability to identify credible sources and use information effectively, limited attention has been given to undergraduates' awareness of IL programmes and their participation in these programmes.

This situation underscores the need to investigate the awareness and participation of undergraduate students in IL programmes for the use of digital information resources in selected universities in Kano State.

Objectives

The main objective of the study is to investigate the awareness of and participation in an information literacy programme among undergraduate students for the use of digital information resources in selected universities in Kano State. Therefore, the specific objectives of the study are:

1. To determine the level of awareness of information literacy programmes for the use of digital information resources by undergraduate students in selected universities in Kano State.

2. To examine the extent of participation of undergraduate students in information literacy programmes for the use of digital information resources in the study area.

Literature Review

Information Literacy Programme Awareness and Use of Digital Information Resources

Studies have shown that awareness of information literacy (IL) programmes strongly influences students' ability to access and use digital information. However, awareness varies widely across institutions and regions. Recent research has reported low student awareness of IL initiatives in several Asian universities, with many students remaining unfamiliar with available digital literacy programmes (Qinling, 2022). In contrast, studies of higher education institutions in India found relatively high IL awareness among postgraduate students, although many still require additional workshops and online training to strengthen their digital competencies (Kumar & Singh, 2020). Evidence also shows that IL awareness improves substantially when IL content is integrated into subject-specific instruction, leading to better learning outcomes and increased confidence in using digital resources (Simon, 2024).

Several recent studies have reported moderate to high levels of awareness of tools such as OPACs, e-resources, and institutional repositories (Manthiramoorathi et al., 2019). Findings from African institutions, including South Africa, Uganda, and Nigeria, show that awareness of IL and digital resources remains uneven and often low, reducing students' effective use of digital platforms (Ndagire & Kyobula, 2021). Conversely, some institutions report satisfactory awareness levels, although this does not always translate into consistent or proficient use of digital resources (Amadi & Igwe, 2015). Overall, awareness of IL programmes remains a critical but insufficient condition for effective use of digital information resources, as awareness does not always translate into frequent or skilled use.

Extent of Participation in Information Literacy Programmes

Active participation is essential for students to develop meaningful information literacy (IL) skills. However, engagement levels vary with factors such as awareness, perceived relevance, curriculum integration, and institutional support. Research consistently shows that IL programmes embedded within the curriculum promote higher participation and stronger learning outcomes than one-off workshops (Henderson, Nunez, & Casari, 2021). Students' perceptions also influence participation. Recent studies show that many still overestimate their IL competencies and therefore undervalue formal training, whereas those who acknowledge their skill gaps demonstrate higher motivation to engage (Godbey & Gordon, 2020). Several studies have reported low attendance at IL activities. For example, Matlatse and Mthethwa (2020) found that many students at South African universities did not participate in library orientation sessions due to limited awareness and perceived irrelevance. Similarly, Chow and Wong (2020) observed disciplinary differences in IL self-efficacy, suggesting the need for customised IL interventions. Conversely, other empirical studies demonstrate moderate to high participation in IL training, particularly when programmes emphasise practical, hands-on learning. Mungwabi (2019) reported that participation in IL activities moderately enhanced students' research and digital skills. Participation has also been linked to measurable improvements in critical thinking, academic writing, and overall academic performance. Institutional studies further highlight the positive impact of IL engagement. For instance, Henderson, Nunez, and Casari (2021) documented significant increases in students' confidence and familiarity with IL concepts after sustained instruction, while Bashorun et al. (2020) found a strong relationship between participation in user-education programmes and students' proficiency in library use. More recent research confirms that targeted IL instruction substantially improves students' digital search and evaluative competencies, although challenges persist in accessing advanced digital tools such as OPAC and external

scholarly databases (Haruna & Bappah, 2022). Overall, participation in IL programmes is shaped by curriculum design, student attitudes, and institutional support.

Methodology

The study adopted a quantitative research method, which was considered appropriate for covering a wide geographical area and a large population of undergraduate students across three selected universities in Kano State. A cross-sectional survey design was employed to collect data from a large sample within a single time frame, making it well-suited to the scope and objectives of the study. The study population comprised 12,818 final-year undergraduate students from Bayero University Kano, Northwest University Kano, and Skyline University Kano. Using proportionate random sampling, a sample of 388 respondents was selected to be representative of the population. Data were collected using a structured, closed-ended questionnaire. The instrument's validity was established through face and content validation. Reliability was confirmed through a pilot test and Cronbach's Alpha, with all constructs exceeding the acceptable threshold of 0.70, indicating strong internal consistency. The quantitative data were analysed using descriptive statistics, including frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations, in SPSS version 23.

Table 1: Population of the study and Sample Size for each of the universities:

S/N	Name of Universities	Status	Number of final year undergraduates	Sample size
1	Bayero University (BUK)	Kano Federal	8668	262
2	Northwest University Kano (NUK)	State	3719	113
3	Skyline University, Kano (SUK)	Private	431	13
	Total		12818	388

Results and Discussion

A total of 388 questionnaires were administered to the respondents. Of this number, only 355 were retrieved, yielding a high overall response rate of 91.5%. The data collected was analysed and presented in line with the research questions formulated for the study.

RQ1: What is the level of awareness of information literacy programmes on the use of digital information resources among undergraduates in the study area?

The Infosphere Statement	Nigerian Journal of Knowledge and Information Studies Vol. 1 (1 & 2) April 2026	BUK		NUK		SUK		Total		TF	M	SD	Remark		
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%						
I am aware my institution offers Lectures/ Orientation s on digital Information resources	BUK	170	47.9	40	11.3	0	0	23	6.5	7	2	240	4.48	.963	EA
	NUK	62	17.5	30	8.5	0	0	1	0.3	9	2.5	102			
	SUK	11	3.1	2	0.6	0	0	0	0	0	0	13			
	Total	243	68.5	72	20.3	0	0	24	6.8	16	4.5	355			
I know my institution organises Workshops /Seminars on digital Information resources.	BUK	49	13.8	13	38	38	10.7	11	3.1	7	2	240	3.89	2.90	SA
	NUK	23	6.5	25	7	31	8.7	15	4.2	8	2.3	102			
	SUK	8	2.3	5	1.4	0	0	0	0	0	0	13			
	Total	80	22.6	165	46.5	69	19.4	26	7.3	15	4.2	355			
I know my institution offers the production of user guides/manuals on digitalisation.	BUK	22	6.4	45	13	6	1.7	8	2.3	15	46	240	2.13	1.52	SLA
	NUK	6	1.7	14	4.0	20	5.8	1	0.3	52	15	93			
	SUK	8	2.3	4	1.2	0	0	0	0	1	0.3	13			
	Total	36	10.2	63	17.7	26	7.3	17	4.8	213	60	355			
I am aware my institution teaches one-on-one discourse on digital Information resources.	BUK	43	12.8	98	29.3	22	6.2	55	16.4	22	6.6	240	3.11	1.41	SA
	NUK	17	5.1	14	4.2	5	1.5	15	4.5	31	9.3	82			
	SUK	0	0	2	0.6	1	0.3	0	0	10	3	13			
	Total	60	16.9	114	32.1	28	7.9	86	24.2	67	18.9	355			
I know my institution organises library tours on digital Information resources.	BUK	12	36.1	30	8.5	42	5.7	3	0.9	38	10.8	240	3.84	1.44	SA
	NUK	48	13.6	11	3.1	23	4.5	3	0.9	14	4	99			
	SUK	9	2.9	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	13			
	Total	184	51.9	41	11.5	69	19.4	8	2.3	53	14.9	355			
I am aware my institution teaches referencing	BUK	17	4.8	52	14.6	12	3.4	7	2	15	42.8	240	1.96	1.46	SLA
	NUK	10	2.8	13	3.7	0	0	1	0.3	78	22	102			
	SUK	0	0	2	0.6	1	0.3	0	0	10	2.8	13			

and Citation Management (e.g., Zotero, EndNote, Mendeley, RefWorks)	Total	27	7.6	67	18.9	13	3.7	8	2.3	240	67.6	355			
I am aware that my institution offers research Data Management (Google Drive, OneDrive, or institutional repositories).	BUK	9	2.5	57	16.1	25	7	1	0.3	148	43.9	240	1.94	1.39	SLA
	NUK	7	2	12	3.4	3	0.8	0	0	80	22.5	102			
	SUK	0	0	2	0.6	0	0	0	0	11	3.1	13			
	Total	16	4.5	71	20	28	7.9	1	0.3	239	67.3	355			
I know my institution teaches database Searching Skills programmes (Techniques for using Boolean operators, filters, etc.)	BUK	6	1.7	55	15.5	13	3.7	10	2.8	156	43.9	240	1.85	1.35	SLA
	NUK	6	17	15	4.2	1	0.3	1	0.3	79	22.3	102			
	SUK	0	0	2	0.6	0	0	0	0	11	3.1	13			
	Total	12	3.4	72	20.3	14	3.9	11	3.1	246	69.3	355			
My institution offers One Education Resources (OER) training	BUK	9	2.6	55	15.9	9	2.6	11	3.2	156	45	240	1.82	1.31	SLA
	NUK	0	0	10	2.9	9	2.6	1	0.3	74	21.3	94			
	SUK	0	0	2	0.6	0	0	0	0	11	0	13			
	Total	9	2.5	67	18.9	18	5.0	20	5.6	241	68	355			
My institution teaches Digital Literacy for Career Development (e.g., LinkedIn Learning, Courser)	BUK	30	8.5	25	7	18	5.1	12	3.4	155	43.7	240	1.92	1.45	SLA
	NUK	8	2.3	8	2.3	9	2.5	4	1.1	73	20.6	102			
	SUK	0	0	2	0.6	0	0	0	0	11	3.1	13			
	Total	38	10.7	35	9.9	27	7.6	16	4.5	239	67.3	355			

Grand mean	2.6 9	SA
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Table 1: Opinions of respondents on Level of Awareness of Information Literacy Programmes on the Use of Digital Information Resources

KEY:

Remark = EA=Extremely Aware, MA= Moderately Aware, SA=Somewhat Aware, SLA=Slightly Aware, NA=Not at all aware.

BUK = Bayero University Kano; **NUK** = Northwest University Kano; **SUK**= Skyline University, Kano

F: = Frequency; **%** = Percentage; **TF**= Total Frequency; **M**= Mean; **SD**= Standard Deviation

Table 2 presented respondents’ awareness of information literacy programmes related to the use of digital information resources across Bayero University Kano (BUK), Northwest University Kano (NUK), and Skyline University Kano (SUK). The results indicate varying levels of awareness, with traditional introductory programmes receiving the highest recognition. Lectures and orientations on digital information resources (M = 4.48, SD = 0.96) recorded extremely high awareness, while workshops and seminars (M = 3.89, SD = 2.90), one-on-one discussions (M = 3.11, SD = 1.41), and library tours (M = 3.84, SD = 1.44) were rated as somewhat aware. These findings suggest that general awareness-based programmes are more visible and accessible to students across the universities. In contrast, awareness of specialised digital literacy programmes was notably low. Programmes such as user guides and manuals (M = 2.13, SD = 1.52), referencing and citation management tools (M = 1.96, SD = 1.46), research data management (M = 1.94, SD = 1.39), database searching skills (M = 1.85, SD = 1.35), open educational resources training (M = 1.82, SD = 1.31), and digital literacy for career development (M = 1.92, SD = 1.45) were all rated as slightly aware. This indicates limited exposure to advanced research and career-based digital competencies. The grand mean of 2.69 suggests that respondents were only somewhat aware of digital information literacy programmes overall. Across the institutions, BUK consistently recorded higher awareness levels, likely reflecting stronger institutional provision and visibility of these programmes. NUK and SUK, however, demonstrated considerably lower awareness, particularly in specialised areas such as citation tools, OER training, and data management. Overall, the findings highlight a significant gap between foundational information literacy awareness and more advanced digital skill development.

RQ2: To what extent do undergraduates participate in information literacy programmes for the use of digital information resources in the study area?

Table 3: Opinions of respondents on Level of Participation in Information Literacy Programmes

Statements	UNI	VH		H		AV		L		VL		TF	M	SD	R
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%				
		I have attended Lectures/Orientations on digital Information resources	BUK	49	13.8	132	37.2	403	11.3	19-	5.4-				
	NUK	66	18.6	236	6.5	13-	3.7-	-	-			102			
	SUK	8	2.3	5	1.4	-	-	-	-			13			
	Total	123	34.6	160	45.1	539	14.9	19-	5.4-			355			

I have participated in Workshops/Seminars on digital Information resources.	BUK	28	7.9	122	34.4	56	15.8	23	6.5	11	3.1	240	3.39	1.12	A V
	NUK	18	5.1	16	5.1	39	11	4	1.1	25	7	102			
	SUK	1	0.3	8	2.3	4	1.1	0	0	0	0	13			
	Total	47	13.2	146	41.1	99	27.9	27	7.6	36	10.1	355			
I have received training on how to use user guides/manuals on digitalisation.	BUK	17	4.8	18	5.1	34	9.6	107	30.1	64	18	240	2.27	1.15	L
	NUK	4	1.1	7	2	19	5.4	45	12.7	27	7.6	102			
	SUK	5	1.4	5	1.4	1	0.3	0	0	2	0.6	13			
	Total	26	7.3	30	8.5	54	15.2	152	42.8	93	26.2	355			
I have participated in one-on-one discourse on digital Information resources.	BUK	29	8.2	115	32.4	47	13.2	35	9.9	14	3.9	240	3.26	1.29	A V
	NUK	26	7.3	4	1.1	21	5.9	14	3.9	37	10.4	102			
	SUK	3	0.8	10	2.8	0	0	0	0	0	0	13			
	Total	58	16.3	129	36.3	68	19.2	49	13.8	51	14.4	355			
I have attended library tours on digital Information resources.	BUK	75	21.1	67	18.9	80	22.5	6	1.7	12	3.4	240	3.46	1.35	A V
	NUK	24	6.8	13	3.7	6	1.7	21	5.9	38	10.7	102			
	SUK	3	0.8	9	2.5	1	0.3	0	0	0	0	13			
	Total	102	28.7	89	25.1	87	24.5	27	7.6	50	14.1	355			
I take part in referencing and Citation Management (e.g., Zotero, EndNote, Mendeley, RefWorks) training	BUK	56	15.8	33	9.3	15	4.2	78	22	58	16.3	240	2.41	1.47	L
	NUK	6	1.7	0	0	11	3.1	36	10.1	49	13.8	102			
	SUK	2	0.6	2	0.6	1	0.3	0	0	8	2.3	13			
	Total	64	18.4	35	9.9	27	7.6	114	32.1	51	32.4	355			
I have attended Data Management (Google Drive, OneDrive, or institutional repositories search training session	BUK	48	13.5	40	11.3	5	1.4	65	18.3	82	23.1	240	2.32	1.34	L
	NUK	12	3.4	7	2	12	3.4	5	1.4	66	18.6	102			
	SUK	2	0.6	2	0.6	1	0.3	0	0	8	2.3	13			
	Total	62	17.5	49	13.8	18	5.1	70	19.7	56	43.9	355			

I have participated in database Searching Skills programmes (Techniques for using Boolean operators, filters, etc.)	BUK	7	2	62	17.5	48	13.5	37	10.4	8	24.2	24	2.3	1.3	L
	SUK	1	3.7	6	1.7	12	3.4	17	4.8	5	15.2	10			
	SUK	0	0	3	0.8	1	0.3	1	0.3	8	2.3	13			
	Total	2	5.6	71	20	61	17.2	55	15.5	1	41.8	35			
I have attended One Education Resources (OER) training	BUK	4	12.4	20	5.6	52	14.6	40	11.3	8	23.7	24	2.3	1.5	L
	NUK	1	3.9	8	2.3	6	1.7	4	1.1	7	19.0	10			
	SUK	1	0.3	3	0.8	1	0.3	0	0	8	2.3	13			
	Total	5	16.6	31	8.7	59	16.6	44	12.4	1	45.2	35			
I have participated in Digital Literacy for Career Development (e.g., LinkedIn Learning, Coursera)	BUK	1	3.1	68	19.2	22	6.2	52	14.6	8	24.7	24	2.3	1.4	L
	NUK	1	5.9	2	0.6	6	1.7	0	0	7	5	0			
	SUK	2	0.8	2	0.6	0	0	0	0	7	20.8	10			
	Total	1	9.9	72	20.3	28	7.9	52	14.6	3	6	2			
Grand mean												2.8	Average		
												3			

key: Scale= VH =Very high, H= High, AV=Average, L= Low and VL= Very Low M=MEAN SD= Standard deviation, R= remark.

Table 3 presents respondents' level of participation in Information Literacy Programmes across Bayero University Kano (BUK), Northwest University Kano (NUK), and Skyline University Kano (SUK). The results show considerable variation based on programme type. Participation was highest in lectures and orientations on digital information resources (M = 4.09, SD = 0.84), indicating strong engagement in foundational information literacy activities. Participation in workshops and seminars (M = 3.39, SD = 1.12), one-on-one discussions (M = 3.26, SD = 1.29), and library tours (M = 3.46, SD = 1.35) was rated as average, suggesting moderate involvement in structured, interactive learning formats.

In contrast, participation in specialised digital literacy programmes was notably low. Activities such as the use of user guides and manuals (M = 2.27, SD = 1.15), referencing and citation management tools (M = 2.41, SD = 1.47), research data management (M = 2.32, SD = 1.34), database searching skills (M = 2.32, SD = 1.34), Open Educational Resources (OER) training (M = 2.38, SD = 1.52), and digital literacy for career development (M = 2.30, SD = 1.47) all recorded low mean scores, indicating minimal student participation in advanced, research-oriented, and career-focused digital skills programmes.

The grand mean of 2.83 indicates that overall participation in information literacy programmes was only average. This suggests that while introductory activities are relatively well attended, students participate far

less in specialised digital literacy programmes that are essential for academic research, effective information use, and employability. The pattern highlights the need for universities, particularly NUK and SUK, to expand awareness and strengthen participation in advanced digital information skills to prepare undergraduates for academic and professional challenges.

Discussion of Findings

The first research question examined undergraduates' level of awareness of IL programmes and their use of digital information resources. Findings revealed a generally moderate level of awareness across the universities, particularly concerning workshops, lectures, library tours, and individualised support. Recent studies show similar patterns across global institutions. For instance, Mwiya et al (2025) argued that while students are generally aware of basic IL services, deeper awareness of advanced digital skills training is limited. Likewise, Ayoola and Nwosu (2021) observed moderate awareness among Nigerian university students, noting that awareness increases when IL is integrated into academic activities. The moderate awareness observed indicates partial engagement with IL processes, emphasising the need for universities to deepen awareness through curriculum integration, sustained skill-building, and stronger collaboration between librarians and faculty.

The second research question explored undergraduates' level of participation in IL programmes and its influence on their use of digital information resources. Findings showed an average level of participation, with students more engaged in introductory activities such as lectures, workshops, and library tours. This mirrors recent research findings, showing that students participate most actively in basic IL programmes while demonstrating lower engagement in advanced sessions. For instance, Mungwabi (2019) found that participation in IL programmes moderately improves student skills, though engagement is higher for introductory content. More recent evidence from a study by Henderson, Nunez, and Casari (2021) shows that consistent, scaffolded IL instruction significantly enhances participation and boosts academic confidence. This suggests that while introductory IL activities successfully initiate engagement, they do not sufficiently support deeper, sustained skill acquisition. To address this gap, IL instruction should be fully embedded within academic coursework and progressively scaffolded across levels to enhance participation and the development of digital competencies.

Conclusion

This study concludes that while foundational information literacy (IL) programmes such as lectures, orientations, workshops, library tours, and one-on-one sessions are available to undergraduates in Kano State universities, both awareness and participation remain moderate and largely limited to introductory activities, indicating that current IL initiatives are insufficiently structured to develop higher-order skills such as evaluation, synthesis, and ethical application. These findings highlight the need for scaffolded, skill-based IL instruction integrated into curricula, ensuring students' progress from basic awareness and participation to mastery of comprehensive information problem-solving competencies necessary for effective and independent use of digital resources.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made:

1. Universities should expand IL programmes beyond basic lectures, workshops, orientations, and library tours to include advanced, practical, and discipline-specific training.

2. Library management should strengthen publicity and awareness campaigns using multiple channels such as social media, university portals, and classroom announcements to improve visibility and encourage broader student engagement with IL programmes.
3. Faculties and libraries should embed IL sessions directly into the academic curriculum as compulsory credit-bearing components, ensuring consistent students' participation beyond voluntary or introductory formats.

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